

ABSTRACT

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Ageing and dementia 1

EPO-001 | Development of small molecules promoting tau clearance in Alzheimer disease

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Background and Aims: A major pathological hallmark of Alzheimer disease (AD) is the intracellular accumulations of neurofibrillary tangles composed of paired helical filaments (PHFs) of tau protein. Lowered efficiency of degradation pathways, such as ubiquitin proteasome system, further exacerbates the aggregated tau accumulation. Proteolysis-Targeting Chimeras (PROTACs) are hetero-bifunctional molecules that can bring E3 ligase into the vicinity of protein of interest, leading to protein ubiquitination, followed by proteasomal degradation. Since 2016, PROTACs have been applied to resolve tau pathologies. Most of these PROTACs have only been evaluated in cell models and the exploration is still at the early stage. In this study, we aim to perform intensive research to develop novel small-molecule PROTACs to initiate tau degradation for AD treatment.

Methods: We screened a library of tau binders from a public database (bindingdb.org) by performing global molecular docking into the 3D structure of PHFs. The top ranked compounds were selected to design new PROTACs, with different linkers connected to the ligands binding to E3 ligase, for instance cereblon and carboxyl terminus of Hsp70 interacting protein (CHIP). We are performing modeling of the ternary complex (tau-PROTACs-E3 ligase) and the highly scored PROTACs will be synthesised. Their protein binding affinities and tau-reducing effects will be evaluated in cell models.

Results: We perform the development of small-molecule PROTACs according to the methods listed above. We selected the top ranked tau binders and designed new PROTACs.

Conclusion: The hit PROTACs will move on to in vivo study and provide pre-clinical evidence for novel treatment of AD tauopathies.

Disclosure: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

EPO-002 | Functional connectivity as biomarker of neurodegenerative disease

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Background and Aims: Alzheimer's disease (AD) selectively involves cerebral neuronal networks. The aim was to correlate fMRI patterns and EEG-coherence in Alzheimer's disease (AD), amnesic Mild cognitive impairment (aMCI), non amnesic Mild cognitive impairment (nMCI), Frontotemporal Dementia (FTD) and controls.

Methods: 90 patients with AD, 90 aMCI, 85 nMCI, 60 FTD patients and 90 age-matched controls underwent fMRI (3 Tesla, TRIO, Siemens) and resting EEG-recordings (NeuroScan Synamps System). EEGs were recorded using a standard protocol and montage. Coherences between regions of interest, based on fMRI activation patterns were calculated.

Comparison of controls vs. AD patients. fMRI activations ($p < 0.001$)

Results: There were significant differences between AD and aMCI for theta coherences between anterior cingulate gyrus (ACC) and left temporal gyrus (LTG) (AD < aMCI, $p < 0.05$) Fig.2; between AD and controls for theta between ACC and right temporal gyrus,

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Classifier	Models and Selected Features							
	Baseline		2-hour		24-hour		Discharge	
	1. Age 2. Baseline Systolic Blood Pressure 3. ASPECTS 4. Baseline NIHSS 5. Baseline Hemoglobin 6. Baseline Glycemia 7. Platelet count 8. Usage of Acetylsalicylic acid 9. Onset to treatment time 10. Door to CT time 11. Type of hyperlipidemia 12. OCSPT type of stroke		1. Age 2. ASPECTS 3. Baseline NIHSS 4. Baseline Hemoglobin 5. Baseline Glycemia 6. Platelet count 7. Usage of Acetylsalicylic acid 8. Onset to treatment time 9. Door to CT time 10. 2-hour NIHSS 11. Type of hyperlipidemia 12. OCSPT type of stroke		1. Age 2. Baseline Glycemia 3. Platelet Count 4. Door to Needle time 5. 2-hour NIHSS 6. 24-hour NIHSS 7. Post-dPA, Distal: Blood Pressure 8. OCSPT type of stroke		1. Age 2. Baseline glycemia 3. 2-h NIHSS 4. 24-h NIHSS 5. Door-to-needle time 6. OCSPT type of stroke 7. Discharge NIHSS 8. Discharge treatment 9. Length of hospitalization	
	Evaluation metrics							
	AUC	Accuracy	AUC	Accuracy	AUC	Accuracy	AUC	Accuracy
SVM	0.83	0.79	0.85	0.78	0.91	0.85	0.96	0.90
Logistic Regression	0.84	0.79	0.85	0.76	0.92	0.85	0.96	0.89
Random Forest	0.80	0.72	0.79	0.75	0.89	0.85	0.96	0.87

Selected features and Evaluation metrics

AUC-ROC curves

Conclusion: The baseline model is applicable for predicting clinical outcomes before IVT, aiding in decision-making for its initiation, while other models enhance predictive accuracy for post-IVT clinical outcomes, allowing timely adaptations in treatment approaches.
Disclosure: Nothing to disclose.

EPO-043 | The outcome prediction of ischemic stroke patients with atrial fibrillation: An interpretable machine learning study

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Background and Aims: Considering that patients with atrial fibrillation (AF) can also achieve favorable outcomes, there is a noticeable literature gap in identifying contributing factors and prediction possibilities for this group. The aim was to utilize interpretable machine learning (IML) to analyze the functional outcomes of stroke patients with admission AF.

Methods: We included 381 alteplase-treated acute ischemic stroke (AIS) patients, out of which AF was registered in 29% during admission. Based on the 90-day modified Rankin Scale (mRS) value, two groups were made: a favorable outcome group (mRS ≤2), and

an unfavorable outcome group (mRS ≥3). 63 features were used as input for the analysis and model build-up. The decision-making process was better understood through the interpretation packages.

Machine Learning Model Build-Up Process

Results: In the AF group (n = 109), a favorable outcome was achieved in 55% of patients, and 4 selected distinguishing variables were: the patient's age, the baseline and 24-h value of NIHSS (National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale), and the type of stroke determined by OCSPT (Oxfordshire Community Stroke Project). Logistic regression showed high predictive power (AUC=0.922), and the interpretation packages revealed a 24-h NIHSS value as the most influential factor.

SHAP analysis results – the whole group-level interpretation

LIME analysis results – the individual-level interpretation

Conclusion: By focusing on alteplase-treated ischemic stroke patients with admission AF, this study identified younger age, lower baseline and 24-h NIHSS values, and OCSPT types of AIS other than TACI as important predictors of a favorable 90-day functional outcome. IML can enhance trust and aid in understanding the decision-making 'black box' of machine learning.

Disclosure: Nothing to disclose.